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FORTIFIED PASTA WITH PLANT BASED INGREDIENTS – INFLUENCE ON MICROBIOLOGICAL QUALITY

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ABSTRACT

Pasta is part of everyday diet around the world for centuries. It is made from basic raw materials – flour and water – but various constituents/ingredients can be added. In such a way, fortified pasta is prepared, which possess diverse added values, both, from a nutritional and a health perspective. Microbiological quality is one of the important parameters for fresh pasta. It depends on the consideration of good hygiene practices and microbiological quality of the primary materials. In our research, we were interested in spinach and cinnamon, because of known positive effects for nutrition. The aim of current study was to evaluate influence of selected plant based ingredients in fresh pasta on its microbiological quality.

Fresh pasta microbiological quality parameters were evaluated through monitoring of mesophilic bacteria, yeasts and fungi, as well as *Bacillus cereus* and *Staphylococcus aureus* count over 12 days of monitoring. Results were expressed as the influence on microbiological parameters in relative values, according to the control data.

Monitoring of microbiological parameters showed that cinnamon has good antimicrobial potential as added ingredient in pasta, to inhibit growth of bacteria and fungi. Similar influence on fungi was seen for spinach, while the impact on bacteria was less pronounced. *B. cereus* was detected in all pasta from day 1 of monitoring. Moreover, *S. aureus* was detected only in control pasta after 8 days of storage. To conclude, microbiological quality of raw materials and antimicrobial potential of the ingredients play the crucial role in microbiological quality of the final product - fresh pasta, as it can be improved or worsened.

Keywords: fresh pasta, microbiological quality, plant based ingredients, fortification

INTRODUCTION

Pasta is a product prepared by mixing water and wheat flour (*Triticum aestivum* spp. *vulgare*) or semolina (*Triticum durum*). During the kneading of dough there is a possibility of incorporation of extra ingredients, and as such production of fortified/enriched pasta. After mixing, the dough must have characteristics of crumbly, tiny-lump mass. This process of making pasta is followed by extrusion. While the pressure of extrusion affects pasta dough, it gains plastic and elastic properties (Bushuk, 1985), and its final form. This pressure process also provides minimalistic degradation of nutrients on one hand, and degradation of antinutrients on another (Vukmirović, 2009). Mixing dough and forming it into shape are two most beneficial steps for making good quality pasta.

Pasta is a part of everyday diet throughout the World. One of the main attributes is their ability to deliver low glycemic index (GI=49±2) (www.health.harvard.edu). Also, the contents of fat and proteins are low, and high for complex carbohydrates (Minarovičova et al., 2018). Pasta can be source of many essential micronutrients (vitamins and minerals), and it is one of the largest sources of carotenoids and tocotrienol – vitamin E. It is important antioxidant, playing important role in preventing the oxygen stress and illnesses such as: cardiovascular diseases, cancer, chronic inflammations and neurological disorders.

Incorporation of vegetables, fruits, and plants as ingredients in pasta dough, delivers richer nutritional qualities of final product. Additionally, modern society demands food that can be prepared fast, and be as much as possible rich in nutrients at the same time. This puts pasta in good position, especially new products with improved quality. Usage of plants as extra

ingredients added to pasta dough mixture secures product with economically low price and easy access for consumers.

Plants, their parts, essential oils, extracts and their dried forms, well known as spices, have many bioactivities, antimicrobial effect being just one of them (Nielsen & Rios, 2000). Their wide and sizeable usage throughout preparation of foods, puts spices on the top of highly used ingredients. Although, they are well-known as sources of high initial contamination (Van Doren et al., 2013), majority possess phenolic compounds that have potential for prolongation of shelf life of the final product (Oliviero & Fogliano, 2016). Different bioactivities were also found in previous studies for the plants (incorporated in foods) used in our study. Spinach is antioxidant and antimicrobial, and has potential to prevent cardiovascular diseases. Incorporated in foods, it is a regulator of glycemic index through insulin sensitivity (Naidu, 2000). Also cinnamon delivers some very important functions (anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and glycemic control) (Gruenwald et al., 2010).

In addition to bioactivity, the plant based ingredients are also a rich source of nutrients. Due to deficiency of lysine and threonine in durum pasta, addition of spinach increases proteins in the final product, reaching 4 times bigger amount of proteins in comparison to durum pasta (Filip & Vidrih, 2015). Spinach is also rich in phenolic compounds. Acceptance of pasta made with spinach did not affect final sensorial score (Yadev et al., 2014).

As representative of sweet ingredient in pasta production, we take into consideration cinnamon. Cinnamon as food supplement can appear as thickener and source of bioactive compounds. Incorporated into dough mixture enhances presence of total and available iron (Varela & Fiszman, 2013). Cinnamon represents natural antioxidant, with ability to neutralize single oxygen, and contains high concentration of phenols.

Microbiological quality and safety of fresh pasta is an important parameter, and it can be influenced by non-compliance with good hygienic practices during the production, and by the primary materials.

It is important to distinguish in each food composition the impact of recipe. Basic ingredients which are always present for certain food item and additional ingredients enhancing particular characteristic of food item. Selection of such compounds may belong to group considered as additives or it can be considered as ingredient when added amount is more substantial. In our case we consider our additions as ingredients since they impact also sensorial and nutritional profile of fortified pastas.

The aim of our study was to evaluate impact of selected plant based ingredients in pasta composition on microbiological quality of fortified pasta product.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Pasta was prepared from wheat flour using pasta machine fitted with a tagliatelle die (control sample). Fortified pasta was prepared as blends of flour and plant based ingredients (spinach and cinnamon) at concentration of 10%. Flour and tap water were mixed for 15 minutes to obtain moisture content of 30 g/100 g. Homogenous dough was extruded, fresh pasta samples were packaged and frozen at $-18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until required. Pasta was transported to Laboratory for Food Microbiology, Biotechnical Faculty, University of Ljubljana. Sampling was done at days 1, 4, 8, and 12. Experiments were done in duplicate.

Pasta microbiological quality parameters were evaluated through monitoring of: (i) mesophilic bacteria (ISO 4833-1, 2013) on plate count agar (PCA; Biolife, Milano, Italy) incubated at $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ 3 days; (ii) yeast and moulds (ISO 7954, 1987) on dichloran rose-bengal chloramphenicol agar (DRBC; Biolife, Milano, Italy) incubated at $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ 5 days; (iii) *Staphylococcus aureus* (ISO 6888-1, 1999) on Baird-Parker agar (BP; Biolife, Milano, Italy) incubated at $37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ a to 2 days; and (iv) *Bacillus cereus* (ISO 7932, 2004) on *Bacillus cereus* agar (BC; Biolife, Milano, Italy) incubated at $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ 1 day.

Results are presented as influence of added ingredient on microbiological parameters in relative values (negative or positive percentage) according to the control data, where negative percentage presents negative influence (higher plate counts), and positive

percentage positive influence (lower plate counts) on microbial quality. Percentage was calculated using Equation 1:

$$MI (\%) = \left(1 - \left(\frac{\text{treatment}}{\text{control}}\right)\right) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Influence of added ingredients on microbiological parameters is presented in Table 1. Microbiological quality of the fresh pasta directly depends on the microbiological quality of the primary materials. Thus, most probably spinach initially contributed to the increase in primary mesophilic bacteria load. Then, the positive effect of spinach was shown in comparison with control pasta. In cinnamon, positive effect on mesophilic count was over 30 % on all sampling days, indicating a significant influence. Results for mould and yeast count were inconclusive. Despite the lack of consistency, addition of cinnamon showed the best positive effect on yeast count in fresh pasta. Addition of spinach and cinnamon showed positive influence on mould count, with over 50% positive influence on spinach fortified pasta. Fresh pasta was also tested for the presence of pathogenic bacteria. *S. aureus* was found after 8 days of storage only in control samples, and was not detected in spinach and cinnamon fortified pasta. The inconsistency of the results was also evident in *B. cereus* count. It was present in all pasta from the first day of sampling, with similar results in all observed pasta, but on the last day of sampling the influence of spinach and cinnamon addition became positive (around 30%).

Table 1. Relative influence of spinach and cinnamon addition in pasta on microbiological parameters compared to control (negative percentage indicates higher plate counts compared to control, and positive percentage presents reduction of plate counts compared to control).

Parameter	Time	Spinach	Cinnamon
Mesophilic bacteria	day 1	-30.22 ± 3.42	30.39 ± 1.31
	day 4	-7.69 ± 0.04	48.80 ± 0.89
	day 8	-0.03 ± 0.08	46.66 ± 1.60
	day 12	7.24 ± 0.17	35.07 ± 0.04
Yeast	day 1	-12.97 ± 4.15	6.28 ± 5.76
	day 4	13.98 ± 2.52	34.25 ± 1.03
	day 8	-4.40 ± 6.33	22.68 ± 1.01
	day 12	-28.51 ± 9.16	-4.18 ± 2.02
Fungi	day 1	20.09 ± 0.12	-42.92 ± 15.39
	day 4	52.47 ± 0.20	34.29 ± 9.50
	day 8	14.98 ± 0.13	14.98 ± 0.12
	day 12	51.92 ± 0.53	26.17 ± 6.27
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	day 1	Nd	Nd
	day 4	Nd	Nd
	day 8	Nd	Nd
	day 12	Nd	Nd
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	day 1	0	-22.85 ± 10.67
	day 4	0	-0.11 ± 0.15
	day 8	0	0
	day 12	32.89 ± 0.10	32.82 ± 0.20

Nd – not detected, 0 – no influence/results similar to control

Phytochemicals in relation to human health have been recognized for centuries (Gruenwald et al., 2010). The special place in this is their use in food industry – both, from nutritional and health perspective. However, the importance of the used ingredients for the shelf-life and microbiological quality of the food should not be forgotten. Used ingredients in this research are known for their *in vitro* antimicrobial and antifungal activity to target microorganisms, like *Escherichia coli*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella* spp. and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Özcan & Boyraz, 2000; Gruenwald et al., 2010; Tajkarimi et al.,

2010; Stahl-Biskup & Venskutonis, 2012), or as inhibitors of total mesophilic bacteria, moulds and Enterobacteriaceae counts when applied to different foods. In these cases, different extracts were tested. To our knowledge so far we could not find any published research on influence of selected plant ingredients on microbiological quality of pasta or other foods. However, the use of selected ingredients in pasta has proven to influence nutritional and technological properties as published elsewhere. Spinach incorporation into pasta raised protein levels and antioxidant ability (Filip & Vidrih, 2015; Lee et al., 2002). Also cinnamon increased iron level in wheat based food (Mastura et al., 1999).

CONCLUSIONS

Microbiological quality of the fortified fresh pasta is dependent on the used ingredients. This may have effect on microbiological quality and consequently on shelf life and safety. For that reason each new combination of ingredients in recipe has to be tested for technological feasibility and microbiological characteristics beside sensorial evaluation.

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